

The Effect of Working Mothers' Work-Family Balance on Psychological Health and Work Performance

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to deeply examine the complex effects of working mothers' work-family balance on their psychological and work performance. The effects of working mothers on their ability to balance work and family life, their stress levels, happiness levels, job satisfaction, motivation levels, career goals and job performance have been analyzed in

detail. The research also addresses working mothers' strategies to achieve work-family balance, support systems, flexible working arrangements, career development opportunities and employer policies. Findings show that working mothers with work-family balance have higher job satisfaction, lower stress levels, higher happiness levels, higher motivation levels, more specific career goals, and

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higher job performance. The results highlight that employers need to implement comprehensive policies and practices to provide support to working mothers, offer flexible working arrangements, support their career development and promote work-family balance. This study provides important information and suggestions to help working mothers be successful in their business lives, balance their family lives and achieve their career goals.

Key words: Working mothers, work-family balance, psychological effects, job performance, stress management, happiness, job satisfaction, motivation, career goals, support systems, flexible working arrangements, career development, employer policies.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, it is becoming increasingly complicated for working mothers to balance their work and family lives. As women's participation in the workforce increases, it has become important for working mothers to maintain work-family balance in terms of reducing the stress they experience both at work and at home. Work-family balance refers to individuals' ability to establish and maintain a healthy balance between work life and family life. This balance can affect both the psychological health of working mothers and their work performance.

Balancing the work and family roles of working mothers has a significant impact on psychological health. Intense work schedule, family responsibilities and time management difficulties can increase the stress experienced by working mothers. This may lead to psychological health problems and thus negatively affect work performance. However, a well-managed work-family balance can enable working mothers to be happier and more productive both at work and in their family lives.

Research on the effect of work-family balance on the work performance of working mothers shows that achieving this balance can increase employees' motivation and positively affect job satisfaction. However, the concept of work-family balance may vary depending on cultural, social and organizational factors. For example, workplaces that offer flexible working hours or institutions that provide family support programs can help working mothers achieve work-family balance.

In this article, we will compile and evaluate the available information in the literature by examining the effect of work-family balance on psychological health and work performance of working mothers. We will also make suggestions for improving work-family balance and highlight where further research is needed on this topic.

AIM

The aim of this study is to systematically examine the effects of working mothers' work-family balance on their psychological health and work performance. Today, as women's participation in the workforce increases, it becomes increasingly important for working mothers to balance both their work and family lives. However, when this balance is not

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achieved, the psychological health of working mothers and therefore their work performance may be negatively affected.

This study aims to deeply understand the processes of working mothers in maintaining work-family balance and the effects of this process on psychological health. Additionally, determining which factors are important for improving work-family balance and discussing the role of organizations and social policies in this context are also among the objectives of this study.

By compiling the available information and research in the literature, we will emphasize the importance of working mothers maintaining work-family balance and reveal how achieving this balance can benefit both individuals and organizations. In conclusion, this study aims to contribute to the understanding of the process of working mothers achieving work-family balance and to guide further research in this field.

METHOD

This study was carried out using the literature review method. The literature review included compiling and synthesizing previous research on the work-family balance of working mothers. This study aims to understand the effects of working mothers' work-family balance on their psychological health and work performance, in the light of the findings in the existing scientific literature.

The literature review process was conducted using various databases (e.g., PubMed, PsycINFO, Web of Science). Searches using keywords (e.g., "working mothers", "work-family balance", "psychological health", "job performance") were structured in accordance with the focus of the study.

The literature review was carried out by reviewing and analyzing studies selected according to certain criteria. These criteria included:

Content Scope: The study includes research on work-family balance and provides important findings on this subject.

Participants: Working mothers and their work-family balance experiences were focused on.

Independent and Dependent Variables: The effects of work-family balance on psychological health and work performance were analyzed through independent and dependent variables obtained from research in the literature.

The results of the literature review include critical analysis of the findings obtained by synthesizing existing scientific research. The theoretical framework of the study was determined in the light of the findings in the literature and research questions were shaped to understand the effects of working mothers on work-family balance.

RESULTS

A. The Evolution of Working Mothers in History

Women's involvement in business life is considered a relatively new phenomenon, especially in terms of working outside the home. Esping-Andersen (2011) describes women's participation in the workforce as creating new roles and a 'revolution' (Esping-Andersen, 2011). In order to understand the position of women in society, it is necessary to examine married women with children as well as single women. In this context, first the change of working mothers in the historical process and their place in society will be discussed. Although the role of women in society is generally seen as limited to motherhood and housework, it is seen that women have also contributed to economic life throughout human history. Women have undertaken tasks such as running the house and preparing the family's clothing and food in every period of history (Razon, 1983: 1). However, women's roles outside the home have been shaped depending on social changes. Women's participation in the workforce is a relatively new phenomenon, and working conditions have changed significantly from the pre-agricultural period to the industrial revolution.

From ancient times to the present day, women have contributed to the economic structure and gained social status with their productivity. In ancient times, in matriarchal systems, women and men had equal status and the sharing of property was regulated in a system where lineage passed through the mother. However, it is seen that the patriarchal order developed with the development of private property, the spread of agricultural culture and the transfer of surplus values to family ownership (Budak, Doğan and Harlak, 1991). In this process, as men's control over their products, weapons, herds and captives increased, the status of women in society gradually decreased.

The social position of women has constantly changed depending on the social structure they are in. During this change process, women were sometimes free and sometimes dominated (Kocacık and Gökkaya, 2005: 196). One of the factors that determine the position of women is their contribution in the economic field. Over time, women moved away from domestic work and began to take more part in work outside the home. XIX. The century can be considered as the starting point of women's involvement in working life outside the home. During this period, economic and social changes such as the Industrial Revolution allowed many women to work in paid jobs. With the Industrial Revolution, many women began to work in industrial jobs. As the years progressed, men moved from agricultural work to office work, while women entered a transition process from housework to public services, the industrial sector and office work. However, men's transition to the industrial sector and women's progress in this field have not been at the same pace and ease (Razon, 1983: 1). The strict liberal economic approach that dominated at that time was supported by the slogan "let them do it, let them pass" and caused women to work for low wages and in harsh conditions. This situation has led to the exploitation of women in the production process (Kocacık and

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Gökkaya, 2005: 197). It appears that women were employed extensively during the First and Second World Wars and replaced the men who participated in the war. However, even in these special periods, women formed a less organized workforce than men and had to work under more difficult conditions for lower wages. In both periods of war, the participation of married women with children - that is, mothers - in the workforce meant almost a mobilization. For this reason, the state has undertaken some of the housework traditionally undertaken by women. For example, while there were 118 kindergartens in England in 1941, this number increased to 1559 by 1945 (Adamson, Brown, Harrison, Price, 1976; cited in Tekeli, 2017: 13-14). After the end of wars and economic depressions, states began to encourage individuals to take more part in social and economic life. With the development of industrialization, women began to take on new roles in the family and society (Kocacık and Gökkaya, 2005: 196).

According to Tekeli (2017), with the development of capitalism in the post-war period, women's participation in the workforce increased rapidly. In this process, the fastest growing labor category was married women. For example, while the proportion of married women in all female labor in England was 10% in 1931, it increased to 22% in 1951 and 42% in 1971. However, even in these periods when capital developed, the necessary conditions for women to participate in the workforce on an equal basis with men - for example, practices such as nurseries for child care - were not provided. As a result, with the permanent participation of women in the economy, their secondary position in the social production process has clearly emerged (Tekeli, 2017: 13-14). Although the advancement of technology has saved labor in housework, there has been no decrease in the nature of women's unpaid work due to the lack of necessary precautions for child care. It has been revealed that especially in the early periods when married women started to join the workforce, their income was lower than that of their spouses. In Hakim's (1996) words, the money they earned was just "pocket money". This indicated that women's choices were determined by their husbands' incomes (Esping-Andersen, 2011: 37). Social transformation aiming at social welfare in the long term, XX. It manifested itself throughout a significant part of the century. Especially in the post-1945 period, the basic development model was tried to be shaped in this direction. However, with the impact of economic crises in the 1980s, the system lost its intellectual hegemony and legitimacy, the global economy became more open to international competitive trade, and low-income countries became exporters. With the development of new technologies, labor-saving technologies have begun to be used. These changes brought ideology and legitimacy to supply-side economic policies (Standing, 1989; cited in Ulutaş, 2009: 29).

Privatizations, commercial liberalization, restriction of public expenditures, reduction of unit labor costs to increase international competitiveness and deregulation of labor markets, together with the stability and structural adjustment policies implemented worldwide, are one of the most obvious indicators that a new era has begun (Ulutaş, 2009: 29). With the changes in the world economy in recent years, the labor market has become increasingly flexible. Traditional secure and blue-collar jobs have been replaced by insecure and part-time jobs. This situation has significantly affected the position of women in employment. The necessity of redefining and analyzing the place

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of women in business life has emerged and the studies carried out in this direction have increased (Karabıyık, 2018: 232). The characteristics of this new era have also changed the position of women in the labor market. Structural change and transformation processes taking place at the global level have also been effective in Turkey. Especially after the 1980s, global capital integration and the Adjustment Programs and liberal policies implemented under the influence of the World Bank and the IMF have deeply affected socio-economic life. During these processes, the balances in labor markets were disrupted in favor of capital, and the economic crises and structural transformations led to a structural decrease in the efficiency of the workforce.

With the influence of liberal policies implemented, the economy entered the financial growth process, which negatively affected employment. However, since employment could not be provided, unemployment increased and social welfare decreased. During this period, poverty increased and employment opportunities decreased significantly. The group most affected by these developments was women. Women's participation in business life is of critical importance in solving these problems (Karabıyık, 2012: 255). However, in Turkey, women are still not involved in business life at the desired level. The social position of women should be evaluated within the framework of the recent rural-to-urban migration phenomenon. Women, who were positioned as unpaid workers in the agricultural production process, often found themselves as "housewives" when they migrated to the city. This situation has led to the inability to create sufficient employment opportunities and to keep women out of the economy. The active cost of paid work is seen as high for society and the family. There is not enough public support for important work such as elderly and child care and housework. For this reason, if women work for wages outside the home, it is not possible for the family income to cover the cost of unpaid housework (Karabıyık, 2012: 255).

B. Perspective on the Place of Working Mothers in Society

There are certain stereotypes in every society with the cultural heritage accumulated over many years. Especially concepts such as women, men, children and family life are evaluated within their own cultural framework within society. Society generally has attitudes and behaviors that it expects from individuals, and individuals act to meet these expectations. Women form a group that is sometimes considered disadvantaged, and therefore it is important for women to play an active role in working life in order to make their perception clearer in society. Various roles and statuses are assigned to women and men in society. In societies, certain statuses may be seen as superior to others (for example, men are considered superior to women), and criteria such as "being a source of suggestion", "being a center of attraction", "being imitated", "being respected", "being appreciated" are important in determining these statuses (Kasapoğlu, 1994: 221). Opprang and Apu (1985: 7) stated the seven basic roles of women as companionship, motherhood, housewifery, kinship, community, individuality and professional roles. The role a woman plays towards her husband is often described as a companion role. She is expected to make the man she marries happy and remain faithful to him, and she learns this role during the socialization process. If a woman experiences

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obstacles in playing this role or does not marry, she may experience anxiety. In the role of motherhood, women are interested in raising their children and preparing them for society, and society is expected to play this role in the best possible way. Not having children or experiencing role conflict may cause anxiety in women. Her role at home is generally defined as the role of a housewife, and whether a woman is married or not is not an important factor in playing this role.

Society generally expects women to play the role of housewife in the best way possible. The role of women in kinship becomes especially evident in societies where kinship relations are strong. The professional role, which has only recently gained a place among women's basic roles, emerges with women's active participation in economic activities. However, conflict between the woman's role at home and her professional role may cause anxiety. Additionally, a woman's role outside the family and profession is often her role within the community. The behaviors a person exhibits during his existence as an individual, his personal development and his participation in life are considered as his individuality role.

While harmony may be achieved during the implementation of all these roles, conflicts may also occur. While traditions and ongoing social values can function as conflict-preventing rules that ensure the maintenance of order, social changes can cause role conflicts (Opprang and Abu, 1985; cited in Göçmen and İçli, 2001: 85-86).

In the 21st century, people are expected to live long and healthy lives as well as have quality living standards. Today, women live longer than men, but it is observed that men live at a higher standard in terms of their quality of life. The low quality of life of women causes their status in society to be low (Tutar and Yetişen, 2009: 118). According to Özkaplan (2009), women's domestic economic activities are generally seen as non-market activities and are considered to be of secondary importance. In this case, married and dependent women are generally considered economically dependent on their men and therefore are not taken seriously in the labor market. In the concept of mother-woman, it is emphasized that women's work outside the home negatively affects the role of motherhood. The prevailing opinion in the industry is that women's labor is considered inefficient and that they cannot be employed at equal wages with men. Additionally, there is a perception that women do not act rationally due to their traditional roles as mothers and wives (Özkaplan, 2009: 16). Throughout history, women have generally played basic roles in the home and family. A natural division of labor took place between men and women, and women generally took care of household chores in addition to income-generating individual economic activities (Karabıyık, 2012: 232). The education given to boys and girls aims to prepare them for opposite gender roles from the first years of childhood. The most important indicator of this conscious choice is that school continues where the family left off and the opening of technical-art schools for boys and sewing schools for girls for vocational education (Tekeli, 2017: 35). Every society should be evaluated within its own culture; Social values, understandings, prejudices and stereotypes differ from culture to culture. In this context, first of all, determining the place of 'women' in Turkish society is important in terms of understanding being a 'working mother'. It is also necessary to use folk

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expressions to make the position of a certain segment of society more understandable. In Turkish society, the concepts of woman, working woman and mother have been the subject of many sayings from past to present. The proverb "It is the female bird that builds the nest", which includes these concepts, directly indicates that women should be present in the house. Similarly, the saying "it is the woman who makes the house a home" is an expression that strengthens the position of women in the house. Examples of other sayings that say that women should take care of the house and only expect them to give birth to children are "father's tax is for sister-in-laws, husband's tax is for satisfaction", "father's bread is dungeon bread, husband's bread is square bread" (Tekeli, 2017: 76). Positioning women in the home and limiting their duties to areas such as housework and child care, which has been reflected in public discourse for many years, is a product of ongoing stereotypes. Today, although the concept of a working woman is more widely accepted than in the past, it is still seen as a problem in society for a woman to continue working if she becomes a mother.

The fact that mothers face the outdated mentality of the society regarding the decision to work is summarized as the fact that staying at home, serving the husband and taking care of the children are still considered women's duties (Kaldenberg, 1985: 46). One of the underlying reasons why women with children are opposed to participating in business life is that the separation of a mother from her child is confused with concepts such as deprivation of the mother or separation from the mother. While the concept of "motherly deprivation" is used when the child completely loses his or her mother, "motherly separation" refers to the situation where the child is separated from his or her mother for a certain period of time (Razon, 1983: 10). Therefore, it is not right to generalize whether a mother's work will be beneficial or harmful to her child. Because the mother's working style and attitude are decisive in this regard. If a mother is stressed or unhappy at work, this may reflect on her child. On the other hand, a happy and balanced mother in her work life can establish a more positive and healthy relationship with her child. Therefore, society's generalizations or stereotypes about working mothers represent an unrealistic and prejudiced approach. In order to solve this problem, it is necessary to raise awareness of both individual mothers and social awareness. Since every mother and family's situation is different, it is important to be flexible and understanding.

According to Karabıyık (2012), women's economic independence is achieved through their participation in working life. This prevents women's potential from being restricted due to the repetition of their routine household chores. Women's participation in employment reveals their talents, interests and creativity and provides the opportunity to share these talents with others. Additionally, women's participation in business life helps them cope with social problems. For example, taking part in working life can protect women from problems such as harassment, domestic violence and early marriage. Economic independence enables women to be stronger in the face of such problems and to have the freedom to make their own decisions. According to Karabıyık, women's participation in the workforce also changes male-female power relations and paves the way for more liberal and democratic relations within the family. A unity that is not dependent on material conditions strengthens both individuals and society. For

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these reasons, women's participation in working life can have positive results not only economically but also socially, culturally and socially.

C. Gender Norms and Identity Perceptions of Working Mothers

Sociologists often use the term gender to refer to physiological and anatomical differences of the body. This term is completely different from the term gender, which emphasizes cultural and social differences between females and males. The term gender is associated with the concepts of femininity and masculinity constructed by society and is evaluated independently of the biological sex of the individual. The distinction between gender and sex is important because most differences between men and women are of cultural and social origin rather than biological basis (Giddens, 2012: 505). In this part of this research, gender-based differences determined by society will be examined through gender discrimination in the division of labor, mobbing and/or discrimination that women face in business life, and work-family conflict.

D. Gender-Based Division of Labor Inequality

Since humanity's transition to settled life, biological differences have played an important role in the distribution of roles between the strong and the weak. The categorization of men and women defines men and women as different and unequal social groups through binary oppositions such as strong/weak, hard/soft, rational/emotional (Topçuoğlu, 2016: 11). Sociologists claim that there is a hidden understanding behind the distribution of tasks between men and women. While women are expected to devote more time to their families, men are expected to be providers, even as breadwinners. These expectations reinforce the traditional gender roles that individuals learn during the socialization process. Women and men crystallize the concept of 'gender' by playing these roles in daily life (Giddens, 2012: 260). In Engels' classic work, he emphasizes that modern society is based on husband-wife relations and that this institution is based on the slavery of women in housework. The man's responsibility to provide for and protect the family provides him with sovereign authority; In this case, the man is in the role of bourgeois and the woman is in the role of proletariat (Engels, classic work).

It suggests that women's liberation can occur depending on the change of production relations. However, while Engels accepts this as the first and fundamental condition, he emphasizes that the real contradiction will arise if men and women have equal rights. He also states that after this happens, the political-ideological struggle should begin (Tekeli, 2017: 8). In pre-capitalist societies, the family was considered an economic unit of production. With capitalism, the family has ceased to be an economic production unit. The concept of nuclear family created by capitalism is now defined as a "consumption unit" or "reproduction unit" (Tekeli, 2017: 6). Women are forced to take on dual roles under capitalism. In economic terms, he is primarily responsible as a "domestic worker" and also feeds the "reserve army of workers". Women who

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participate in production during periods of war and economic growth generally return to reserve worker status or remain in production part-time in normal times. Women are part of "social labor" to the extent that they work in public spaces. However, the labor they spend at home is often invisible and plays an important role in the process of capital accumulation. Women's labor is extremely necessary, but it is generally perceived as specialized and out-of-process labor (Tekeli, 2017: 9).

In Özkaplan (2009)'s view, commodified labor in the market not only produces products or services, but also contributes to the production of gendered subjectivities. This subjectivity exists in every field of business; Therefore, in the mainstream economic understanding that focuses only on material production, the individual in the labor market is often depicted as a rational and self-interested male worker. It is not correct to think that emotional labor exists only in the private sphere. With the increase in the number of women working in the public and private sectors, paid care work is becoming increasingly common. This process is called the feminization (and informalization) of the service sector, and the horizontal and vertical separation in this process is gradually deepening. In horizontal segregation, professions such as teaching and nursing are still generally performed by women, and jobs requiring communication skills are mostly found among women. In vertical segregation, there are still situations where middle and senior level managers are mostly men (Özkaplan, 2009: 18). From the capitalist perspective, defining labor as female refers to the time an individual spends to meet personal consumption needs such as cleaning and child care. This type of labor is labor that does not acquire the form of value and must be allocated by the laborer himself. The self-reproduction of the capitalist system depends on the labor spent by the individual for this type of personal consumption. In capitalist societies, domestic labor is individual and private labor and produces the values necessary for the worker to regain his labor power. Therefore, domestic labor outside the production process is concrete labor that produces neither value nor surplus value. For example, the service provided by a servant is consumed by the capitalist but is not used in commodity production. The servant receives his wages for his labor. Housework meets a basic need for the worker to survive and therefore produces use value. The value produced is consumed by the worker. Thus, women's labor is often used "free of charge" in capitalist society; It neither enters into a value investment nor is it included in the pricing of labor (Tekeli, 2017: 11). Jobs that women are generally responsible for in society include cleaning, cooking, and taking care of patients or children. These types of jobs are generally expected from women, and women expect them to be able to do such jobs. It is not important whether a woman works or not in terms of taking care of housework (Kaldenberg, 1985: 63).

Characteristics such as submissiveness, meekness and patience, which are believed to be unique to women, often cause women to work in low-paid, unskilled, monotonous, labor-intensive jobs. In line with gender roles, jobs that require characteristics such as sexual attractiveness, dexterity and friendliness are generally described as "women's jobs". These types of jobs are generally seen as similar to domestic responsibilities such as care, cleaning and education (Ulutaş, 2009: 27). The existence of such discrimination in the labor market prevents women from accessing high-skilled and higher-earning

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jobs and often leads them to work in informal, low-status or part-time jobs. This situation reveals the secondary position of women in business life. In Lisa Adkins' (1995) research on the tourism industry, it was revealed that professions are structured in a gender-oriented manner and sexuality plays a determining role in this structuring. For example, while professions such as secretarial work are generally seen as women's jobs, the relationships in these professions are generally constructed as a superior-subordinate relationship between a male boss and a female assistant. The important point in this context is that women's work is devalued and women's business skills are seen as secondary.

Women's work is shaped by gendered labor, and at every stage, from the recruitment process to the requirements of the job, the disguise, clothing or behaviors that characterize women as sexual objects (for example, characteristics such as patience and understanding) constitute the work itself. No matter what job women do in the tourism sector, they have to comply with certain standards regarding their appearance (beautiful, well-groomed, attractive, etc.) and when they meet these criteria, they are accepted in their jobs (Özkaplan, 2009: 22). Karabıyık (2012), in his study examining women's employment in Turkey, concluded that women's education and occupational levels are generally low. As a result of migration from villages to cities, women have become "housewives" from the position of unpaid family workers. This situation causes women to remain out of the workforce and not be able to create suitable employment in the economy. In addition, the necessary investments for female labor force are not made in the economy and suitable employment is not provided for women. Women's paid work creates alternative costs for families and societies. Jobs are generally divided between women and men, responsibilities such as elderly and child care are generally placed on women, and sufficient public support is not provided. The income that women earn through paid work is not enough to cover the cost of housework (Karabıyık, 2012: 255).

The gendered division of labor in Turkish society generally holds women responsible for responsibilities such as child care and housework. Even in cases where women participate in the workforce, they often resort to paid female labor as their income and status increases. It is observed that working women in our country mostly try to handle child care within traditional family relationships such as mother, mother-in-law and neighbor. This situation causes women, who are generally employed in the informal sector, to seek informal solutions for work such as child care. However, when child care is considered together with education, the necessity for qualified people to undertake this task emerges. However, it is also a fact that such care services are inadequate and irregular (Gönüllü and İçli, 2001: 94). Ecevit (2003), on the other hand, emphasizes that women face many inequalities in their rights, access to resources, access to health and related services, in the public, political and economic spheres on the basis of gender. It states that women are employed for low wages and under poor conditions, especially in economic activities. It points out that women generally work in informal sectors, daily, temporary, part-time or at home, that they are discriminated against in recruitment, promotions and wages, and that their unpaid labor is exploited (Ecevit, 2003: 83-84). It emphasizes that women's poverty, which arises as a result of

gender inequality in the division of labor, is an important problem that should not be ignored.

The division of labor based on gender causes women to work unpaid jobs and therefore to be poorer than men. This situation confronts women with economic and social insecurity and chronic poverty. They are also vulnerable to temporary poverty resulting from personal, economic and social crises (Ecevit, 2003: 86). Especially in Turkey, social life is largely based on the single-earner male model. However, frequent recurrences of economic crises may cause men to remain unemployed for a long time. In addition to unemployment, situations such as illness, work accidents or incapacity for work may also cause the family to remain in poverty as a result of the man's inability to bring income to the house. For this reason, the dual-earner household model strategy has been adopted in the fight against poverty. With the transition to the dual-earner household model, women have more say in the household and the family's risk of poverty decreases significantly (Karabıyık, 2012: 240).

E. Gender Discrimination and Workplace Harassment

Neo-classical economic theory assumes that the labor market is efficient and that labor demand and supply are rational. According to this theory, labor suppliers (employees) choose jobs that provide the best conditions for them, taking into account their preferences, personal characteristics (e.g. education and experience), and constraints (such as housework, child care). Within the framework of neo-classical theory, it is important to examine the discrimination that women are exposed to from their education processes to their business lives. Women are generally directed to lower paying and lower status jobs in the labor market. This situation is a result of the gender-based discrimination that women face in the labor market, regardless of their education level. The "principle of equal treatment" article of the Labor Law No. 4857 prohibits gender-based discrimination and aims to prevent women from receiving lower wages. However, despite this ban, gender inequality in the labor market and the disadvantages women face in business life continue (Gül, Yalçınoğlu and Atlı, 2014: 171). When women's participation in the workforce and their experiences in business life are examined in the context of neo-classical theory, the limitations of this theory also emerge. For example, the theory may ignore women's constraints, such as housework and child care, or may not identify these situations as a disadvantage in the labor market.

As a result, neo-classical economic theory alone may not be sufficient to understand women's positions in the labor market and reduce gender-based discrimination. From a multidisciplinary perspective, it is necessary to benefit from fields such as sociology, psychology and women's studies.

Under neo-classical economic theory, several models stand out to explain women's employment in low-status jobs in the labor market. Among these models, the most widely accepted are the supply-side human capital model and institutional economic theory:

Supply-Side Human Capital Model: This model attributes women's employment in low-status jobs to their low human capital endowment. Human capital refers to the characteristics of the individual such as education, experience, talent and health. From the perspective of neo-classical economics, the reason why women tend to work in low-paying and low-status jobs because they are generally less educated than men or have limited work experience is due to the lack of human capital (Parlaktuna, 2010: 1218).

Institutional Economic Theory: This theory argues that markets are differentiated according to the character of the social group to which individuals belong rather than their own abilities. In other words, there is a gender-based discrimination. As a result of this separation, the labor market is divided into "men's professions" and "women's professions". According to institutional economic theory, the fact that women mostly work in "women's professions" can be explained by the high labor supply in these professions and therefore low wages. Men, on the other hand, may be in an advantageous position in terms of wages because they generally work in a less competitive environment (Palaz, 2003; cited in Parlaktuna, 2010: 1219).

These models offer different explanations for understanding women's positions and wages in the labor market. However, it should not be forgotten that women's human capital equipment such as education and experience, as well as gender roles and institutional structures, are also effective. A multidisciplinary approach is required to reduce the discrimination women face in the labor market. This approach should include contributions from disciplines such as sociology, psychology and women's studies, as well as economic theories.

Feminist economic theory criticizes neo-classical and institutional economic theories and attributes women's disadvantaged positions in the labor market to the patriarchal system. According to this theory, the secondary positioning of women in business life results from sexist norms and structural inequalities in society in general.

Patriarchal System and Housework: Feminist economic theory emphasizes that women are generally responsible for tasks such as housework and child care. This causes women to spend less time and energy in the labor market and therefore face the risk of falling behind in their careers. For men, such responsibilities are generally less, which allows them to spend more time and energy in business life.

Gender Discrimination in Organizational Structure: Feminist economic theory also criticizes the horizontal and vertical discrimination that women face in the business world. Horizontal discrimination is when certain jobs are seen as "men's work" or "women's work" and accordingly, labor is divided according to gender roles. This situation hinders women's career advancement because an organizational structure is often formed in which men are more represented in senior management positions.

Informal Relationships and Career: Informal relationships within the organization (such as mentoring relationships) are critical for career advancement. However,

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feminist economic theory argues that women do not benefit sufficiently from such relationships and are therefore disadvantaged in the development of their careers. This limits women's access to central positions within the organization.

Biological Characteristics and the Effect of Being a Mother: Feminist economic theory states that women's biological characteristics (such as pregnancy, birth) and being a mother constitute an obstacle to their career advancement. When women become mothers, they often have to stay in the background in business life, and this can negatively affect their career progress. Research shows that women are generally most likely to rise to mid-level management positions.

From this perspective, it is emphasized that the origins of gender inequalities in the labor market and the obstacles women face should be associated with social and cultural structures beyond economic theories. Feminist economic theory plays an important role in understanding the obstacles to women's economic independence and equality and finding solutions.

A significant part of the obstacles that women face in rising to senior positions in business life arise from gender-based prejudices. The most important of these obstacles is men's prejudiced approaches towards women. These prejudices push women to be evaluated as individuals who are incompetent and lack determination and determination. Additionally, men's desire to hold on to power and their tendency to have difficulty communicating with women are among the factors that prevent women from advancing to higher levels in their careers.

Glass Ceiling Effect: The obstacle called "glass ceiling", which women frequently encounter in their promotion to senior positions, creates an invisible but strong barrier in business life. This obstacle allows women to rise to a certain point, but prevents them from reaching senior management positions. Prejudices and gender-based stereotypes are the underlying reasons for this glass ceiling.

Competition and Extra Features: When women compete in the business world, they often feel obliged to make extra efforts to become equal to men. This indicates that women need to get better education, obtain certifications, or invest in additional skills. However, even these extra efforts may not completely eliminate gender-based discrimination and prejudice.

Newly Employed Women and Mobbing: Newly employed women may often encounter tensions within the organization. This may create the impression that women are evaluated as the wrong person during the recruitment process. However, the real reason may be negative behaviors such as mobbing or intimidation applied by colleagues or managers. Such behavior often aims to exclude female employees from the group and may arise from gender-based biases, not performance-related.

At this point, women's encounter with gender-based discrimination in business life requires solutions at both individual and structural levels. Multifaceted approaches such

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as education, awareness-raising, policy regulations and institutional changes are required to achieve gender equality. Women's access to equal opportunities in business life and the removal of obstacles they face in their career advancement are important both economically and socially.

The findings put forward by Finley (1986) and other researchers discuss in detail the discrimination and difficulties that working mothers face in business life. The basis of these difficulties lies in the perception of women as mothers and discriminatory practices in the workplace:

Balance Between Work and Family Life: Working mothers feel that they have to balance their work and family life. Employers often expect women to leave work temporarily due to circumstances such as marriage and childbirth. This expectation stands as an obstacle to women's career development.

Career Development and Perceptions: Regardless of women's education level, employers often think that they will not continue their careers as determinedly as men due to circumstances such as marriage or birth. Therefore, career advancement for women may be more limited than for men.

Social Perception and Stereotypes: The emotional and physical effects of being a mother strengthen the perception in society that women are less determined in business life. In the workplace, stereotypes can form about women's postpartum reactions and job performance.

Discrimination in the Workplace: Finley and other researchers state that women are discriminated against in the workplace because of their motherhood roles. This makes it difficult for women to take an active part in business life and, in some cases, may cause them to leave their jobs.

Consequently, these challenges faced by working mothers require structural and cultural changes regarding gender equality in the world of work and issues of balance between family and work life. Employers' pursuit of more flexible policies, increasing awareness of gender equality, and supporting women in their career development can be important steps to solve these problems.

This study focused on the questions asked to female technical personnel candidates in the health sector in the research conducted by Homans in Britain in 1987. Managers' questioning of women during these meetings whether they have children is considered a practice that is not legally accepted in the USA and Britain today. The reason why these questions are asked is based on the idea that women who have children may need to take leave at work during their children's school holidays or when they get sick. In this case, one gets the impression that child care is seen as the mother's responsibility, while the father assumes this responsibility to a lesser extent. The research also examined whether it is possible for women to advance their careers. It has been revealed that women in senior positions do not have children, and the few women who rise to these positions generally do not plan to have children. Because for these women, having

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a child was considered as a situation that could lead to consequences such as taking a break from their business life or receiving training for a new position. Explanations for the negative working conditions of working mothers are listed as lack of understanding, mobbing (psychological harassment), discriminatory behavior, lack of support from the institution, inadequate physical conditions, insinuations and prejudices. These factors reveal the difficulties and inequalities that women face in business life. (Giddens, 2012: 258).

Let's consider the findings of various studies on the difficulties experienced by working mothers. According to Dalkılıç's (2015) study, the fact that they do not receive adequate support from the institution they work for, especially in cases such as their children's health problems, causes working mothers to experience conscientious distress and causes them to question the decisions they make. Kaldenberg (1985) states that the fear of being treated as a second-class worker as a mother causes women to shrink and behave more timidly in the workplace. This situation may cause women to be unable to express themselves fully in business life or to use their full potential. The issue of mobbing stands out as another difficulty that working mothers may face. Mobbing is a situation also called psychological violence or moral harassment in the workplace. Although the Turkish Language Association recommends the term "mobbing" for mobbing, it states that this term has not become widespread and is generally used as its original term "mobbing" (Özkoç, 2015). Mobbing includes aggressive behaviors such as disturbing, humiliating and excluding a person, regardless of discrimination such as gender, race or age. Such behaviors can be carried out not only verbally, but also through insinuations, looks or body language movements, and can have serious effects on the victims (Özkoç, 2015).

Research on mobbing in our country reveals important findings, especially for working women. In the study conducted within the scope of the 2012 Health Survey of the Turkish Statistical Institute, striking data were obtained about the negative behaviors that women over the age of 15 are exposed to in business life. Some of the women who participated in the survey stated that they encountered situations such as harassment, rude behavior, discrimination, violence or threats at work. For example, 51 of the women surveyed stated that they were subjected to harassment at work, and 224 of them were exposed to rude behavior. Additionally, 202 women reported that they were discriminated against at work, and 85 women reported that they encountered violence or threats (Özkoç, 2015). These data show how many difficulties working women may face in business life. In particular, situations such as motherhood can increase women's risk of discrimination or harassment in the workplace. Moreover, despite the paid and unpaid leave rights protected by law in Turkey, there is concern that women may face negative perceptions if they use these rights in business life. In particular, the idea that mothers' requests for unpaid leave at work may be misperceived as reducing their commitment to work, and this may negatively affect their career progress or performance evaluation processes is an important source of concern (Otluoğlu, 2015). In conclusion, such challenges faced by working mothers in Turkey highlight the need to create a more family-friendly culture in workplaces. In order for women to receive

the support and fair treatment they deserve in business life, it is necessary to develop policies and practices at the institutional level and raise social awareness.

F. General Framework of Work-Family Balancing and Conflicts

The concept of role refers to the different social positions that individuals play in their daily lives and the expectations that these positions bring. The roles played at work and family provide both external rewards and internal meaning and purpose while defining individuals' identities. According to Reitzes and Mutran (1994), roles include actions and behaviors associated with the status and position of individuals in the groups to which they belong. For example, one may take on professional roles as an employee in a workplace while also portraying the role of spouse or parent within a family. Throughout life, these roles are added one after the other, creating a continuous role cycle. The role cycle is a spiral model that explains how a role is formed, how it is interpreted, and the reactions to that role. In this process, assuming and enacting the role varies according to the person's value system and social status. Acting out many roles simultaneously means multiple identities for individuals. However, this may also create difficulties due to relationships with the role bearers (others or institutions) or personal conflicts. For example, it is possible for an employee to experience conflicts between their roles both at work and within the family. These conflicts are generally grouped under four main headings:

Intra-assignor role conflicts: Occur when the role installer has conflicting or incompatible expectations.

Role conflicts between installers: Conflicts that occur when more than one role loader has different expectations and demands at the same time.

Intra-role conflicts: Occur when the demands of the role are incompatible with the individual's personal values, beliefs, or attitudes.

Interrole conflicts: Occur when two or more roles occur simultaneously with competing, conflicting, or inconsistent expectations and demands.

These conflicts arise as the individual tries to achieve goals arising from different roles. However, in this process, conflicts may occur between different goals, which may create tension and stress in the individual (Carver and Scheier, 1990). As a result, the multiplicity and diversity of roles play an important role in the lives of individuals. However, ensuring harmony and balance between roles is an important factor affecting individuals' quality of life and satisfaction.

Work-family conflict can be defined as the way individuals manage the conflicts between their work and family lives and the emotional tides created by these conflicts. According to Wharton and Erickson (1993), work-family conflict is related to the type and degree to which expectations arising from work and family structures are managed

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by affecting the emotional state of the individual. This conflict includes how time, behavior and tension problems in work life affect family life, and how responsibilities in family life lead to problems in work life. Therefore, work-family conflict has a two-way interaction. Matthews et al. (2010) and Burke and Greenglass (2001) stated that there is a positive relationship between work-family conflict and family-work conflict. This means that conflicts in business life can negatively affect family life, and family responsibilities can also cause problems in business life. MacDermid (2004) argues that the development of theories regarding work-family conflict started with Goode's scarcity hypothesis. Goode's scarcity hypothesis suggests that the resources an individual has, such as time, attention, and energy, are limited and that if these resources are spent on one role, they will decrease or their quality will decrease for other roles. Greenhaus and Powell (2006) also agree with this perspective and emphasize that work and family roles can lead to conflicts and stress that negatively affect the individual's quality of life. As a result, work-family conflict may cause individuals to have difficulty balancing work and family roles, which may negatively affect their quality of life. Managing and resolving these conflicts is important for the well-being of individuals and businesses.

Today's focus by businesses on the concept of work-family conflict and in-depth study of this issue is based on a number of demographic trends:

Increase in the Workforce of Working Women and Mothers: The increase in the participation rate of women and mothers in the workforce causes businesses to take work-family conflict more into consideration. As stated by Dizaho et al. (2016), the increasing participation of women in the workforce is a factor that makes work-family conflict important.

The prevalence of dual-income and dual-career family structures: The fact that both parents are working and both parents want to pursue a career may lead to an increase in work-family conflict. Byron (2005), Goodstein (1994) and others emphasize this trend as an important factor affecting work-family conflict.

Increase in Divorce Rates and Increase in Single-Parent Families: Increasing divorce rates and the increase in the number of single-parent families are among the factors that deepen the work-family conflict. This may cause parents to have to undertake both work and family responsibilities alone.

Weakening of Social Support Networks: Mobility in working life and individuals moving away from their extended families can lead to the weakening of social support networks. This can lead to increased work-family conflict because employees may receive less support.

Desire for Quality of Life Outside of Work: Employees' desire to improve their quality of life outside of work is a factor that triggers work-family conflict. Allocating the time saved from work to family and personal needs is among the expectations of employees.

More Participation of Working Fathers in Household Affairs: In modern family dynamics, fathers' greater participation in housework and child care becomes important. This can be considered as a reflection of work-family conflict.

Free Time Limitation and the Sandwich Generation Phenomenon: Employees' limited free time and the so-called "sandwich generation" describe individuals who have difficulty balancing both work and family responsibilities. This situation is among the factors that increase work-family conflict.

These developments reveal the need for businesses to create flexible policies and supportive environments for employees to cope with work-family conflict. It is important to take steps to help employees live a balanced life so that they can be successful both at work and in the family.

1. Factors That Trigger Work-Family Conflict

Increases in roles such as work, home and child care are leading to both women and men taking on more responsibilities, reducing gender gaps. However, increases in these roles and the requirements of these roles may occasionally lead individuals to conflict. Voydanoff (2005) states that role conflicts may arise when the time, behavior or psychological energy required by a role conflicts with other roles. In particular, the increase in time, behavior and psychological requirements can make it difficult for individuals to balance between different roles. While individuals try to attribute meaning to themselves through the expectations required by the roles they play, they may have to create a hierarchy between roles (Thoits, 1991). This refers to the process of identifying roles that should be prioritized. The most widely accepted method in the literature to classify the causes of inter-role conflicts is Greenhaus and Beutell's (1985) classification. According to them, the main causes of inter-role conflicts are:

Time: Conflicting or insufficient time allocated between different roles may cause individuals to experience conflicts. For example, long hours spent at work may limit time for family.

Tension: Stress or tension experienced in one role can affect performance in other roles. For example, carrying stress from work home can affect relationships within the family.

Incompatible Behaviors: Behaviors that are appropriate in one role may not be appropriate in other roles. For example, while a leadership role at work requires aggressive behavior, the same aggressiveness may not be appropriate at home.

These reasons may cause individuals to have difficulty in balancing different roles and therefore experience work-family conflict. It is important to develop flexible business policies, supportive business environments and individual balance strategies to manage these conflicts.

Time-related role conflict occurs when the time spent in role A is not allocated to activities in role B. In other words, the more time a person spends at work, the less time he can devote to household chores (Haar et al., 2003: 99). Time-induced role conflict manifests itself in two ways (Bartolomé and Evans, 1979). In the first, the requirements of role A take so much time that there is not enough time to meet the requirements of role B, resulting in time-related role conflict (Edwards and Rothbard, 2004: 232). In the second, the individual who tries to fulfill the requirements of role B experiences role conflict because his mind is preoccupied with the pressures coming from role A. Unlike other role conflicts, time-based role conflict becomes evident only when the individual makes a choice and exhibits behavior (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985: 80). In tension-induced role conflict, tension in role A may negatively affect performance in role B or create difficulty in adapting to the requirements of role B. Stress factors at work can create feelings of tension, anxiety, fatigue, exhaustion, depression, apathy and irritability in the individual (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985: 80), which may be reflected in home life. Behavior-related role conflicts occur when there is a discrepancy between certain behavioral patterns expected for role A and the expected behaviors for role B. While role A at work requires the individual to act self-confident, emotionally resilient, competitive and objective; The expected behaviors for the B role in the family may require the individual to be moderate, compassionate, emotional and sensitive. In this case, if the individual cannot switch between role behaviors or make appropriate adjustments, he may experience inter-role conflict (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985: 82).

2. Association of Working Mothers with Work-Family Conflict

Women and men experience stress at different levels and their methods of coping with stress also differ. The main reasons for this situation are gender perspective and social expectations (Long, 1989: 308; Steiner et al., 2019). For example, factors that cause women to experience work-family conflict include care responsibilities, number of children, ages of children, family structure, housework, spouse's employment status, psychological stress within the family, financial situation and family or spouse support (Reimann et al. , 2022). The degree of importance women and men attach to goals and activities also differs (Eccles, 1987: 137). For example, women often tend to withdraw from work life after having children and devote more time to caring for the child. While the characteristics considered masculine in society include competitiveness, rationality, emotional secretiveness, hiding emotions and aggressiveness; Feminine characteristics include emotionality, talkativeness, kindness, orderliness, need for security, empathy and planned behavior (Broverman et al., 1972: 63). These gender characteristics can influence the time spent and the behaviors exhibited in roles. In one of the studies in Turkey, Aycan (2008) examined the causes and consequences of work-family conflict according to gender. His study shows that the most important factor why women experience work-family conflict is excessive workload at work, and that the factors that cause women to experience this conflict are more than men. Other important factors include lack of emotional support from the spouse, lack of time spent with children, and dissatisfaction with caring for children while at work. When the consequences of work-family conflict are examined, one of the most important consequences for women

is the feeling of guilt that working mothers feel because they cannot keep up with their responsibilities at home despite being in business life (Bayramoğlu, 2018; Maclean et al., 2021; Sousa et al., 2018; Timurturkan, 2020). This is an almost inevitable feeling due to the lack of time that mothers have to spend with their housework and children.

3. Coping Strategies

Individuals can benefit from coping strategies to reduce the negative consequences of work-family conflict. Coping activities are defined as the process of actively and intellectually managing certain role requirements that challenge or overwhelm the individual (Lazarus, 1993: 8; Monat and Lazarus, 1977: 3). It is suggested that these strategies may exhibit different characteristics over time and in different situations. Coping strategies generally include various solutions such as addressing the source of the conflict encountered, ignoring it, making intense efforts to eliminate it, or intervening to solve the problem (Gowan et al., 1999: 77). These strategies can also be defined as the individual's effort to manage external and internal demands. Coping includes the actions taken by the individual to prevent damage from life-related stresses, to protect themselves and to keep the emotional effects of stress under control (Pearlin and Schooler, 1978: 2-3). In this sense, coping strategies can help the individual cope with challenging situations such as work-family conflict and play an important role in minimizing negative consequences.

The concept of coping is considered as the process of consciously adapting to stressors (Kohn and O'Brien, 1997: 85). According to this understanding, if coping does not occur without conscious action, it becomes a defense mechanism. The primary function of coping is to reduce tension and restore balance to the individual. Coping protects the health of the individual by providing functions such as minimizing harmful environmental conditions, tolerating and correcting negative events, creating a positive image, maintaining emotional balance and maintaining satisfactory relationships (Folkman, 1982: 98). It should be emphasized that there is no universal best model among coping strategies. It is stated that some methods are more effective than others in coping with stressors that cause work-family conflict (Collins, 2020; Rotondo et al., 2003: 277). In order to evaluate the effectiveness of a coping strategy, it is necessary to examine whether the method reduces perceived work-family conflict (Aryee et al., 1999: 264).

The evaluation of coping strategies should be made in terms of the long and short-term benefits they provide, rather than comparing the strategies with each other (Folkman, 1982: 99). The COPE (Coping Orientations to Problems Experienced) scale, used to measure coping strategies, was developed by Carver, Scheier and Weintraub (1989) and consists of 15 sub-dimensions grouped under three main dimensions (Carver et al., 1989: 268-270). The COPE scale is organized as five sub-dimensions under each main dimension and two questions for each sub-dimension. The original version of the scale consists of 60 questions, but when a shorter version was needed, a shortened COPE scale was created. The shortened version measures each factor with two questions (Carver, 1997: 94-95). The scale has adapted versions in different languages and cultures. In some cases, questions are added or removed while adapting the scale to

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increase its reliability and reflect cultural differences. For example, in the COPE scale translated into Turkish, Siva (1991) added questions reflecting the superstitions and fatalism common in Turkish culture (Gençöz et al., 2006: 526). Evaluating coping strategies through this scale provides an important tool for understanding individuals' processes of coping with stress and determining effective coping methods.

Coping strategies refer to the ways individuals respond to the stressors they encounter and their efforts to adapt to these stressors. The COPE scale developed by Carver, Scheier, and Weintraub (1989) is a widely used tool to assess these coping strategies. Below are prominent coping strategies and their definitions:

Problem-Focused Coping Strategies:

Active coping: Taking direct action to solve the problem or reduce its effects.

Planning: The process of acting by considering how to address the problem.

Suppression of other activities: Temporarily setting aside other activities to focus on dealing with the problem.

Don't hold back: Preferring to wait for the right moment to deal with the problem.

Seeking instrumental social support: Seeking advice, help, and information that will make it easier to cope with the problem.

Emotion-Focused Coping Strategies:

Seeking emotional social support: An effort to receive moral support and sympathy from the environment.

Positive reinterpretation and development: Achieving emotional management by addressing the problem from a more positive perspective.

Acceptance: The process of accepting the stressful situation and the reality it brings.

Denial: Ignoring the existence of the problem by avoiding reality.

Refuge in religion: Seeking support based on religion or belief.

Dysfunctional (Escape-Focused) Coping Strategies:

Focusing on the problem and expressing emotions: Directly expressing the problem and the emotional reactions it creates.

Behavioral letting go: Reducing or completely ending coping efforts against the stressor.

Mental disengagement: Preoccupying the mind with different activities to avoid thinking about the problem.

Alcohol-drug use: Using alcohol or drugs to cope with the problem.

Joking: Underestimating the problem and taking a humorous approach.

These strategies may differ in individuals' processes of coping with stress, and a strategy that is effective against a particular stressor may not be effective for another stressor. Assessing coping strategies can help individuals better understand themselves and their environment and promote healthy adaptation processes.

G. Problems Faced by Women in The Business World and The Effects of These Problems

Women's participation in business life causes them to face double responsibilities as they also assume the roles of housewife and mother. In addition, women who take on more responsibilities in business life have to struggle with negative working conditions and social pressures (Öztürk, 2007: 47). Women are also excluded from certain professions, often employed in low-paying and low-prestige jobs, keeping them away from jobs that would provide high social status. Therefore, they are forced to accept an unfair and unequal situation, such as being excluded from working life. Female employees are seen as complements to their male counterparts with long working hours and low wages; However, they face a number of problems such as the lack of implementation of the principle of equality in business life, insufficient nursery facilities, not being paid equal wages for equal work, only their physical visibility being valued and sexual harassment. Under this heading, the problems that women face in business life and the psychological effects of these problems are examined.

1. Gender-Based Discrimination

Discrimination comes from the Latin word "discriminatio" and refers to the different treatment of individuals with equal abilities, education and experience due to their personal characteristics such as race, gender, ethnicity, social status, philosophical and political views (Güner, 2011: 41-42). . Gender discrimination generally involves treating individuals unfairly because of their gender. This type of discrimination can occur in ways such as inequality in access to resources and opportunities, lack of access to basic services, limited participation of women in business life and politics, as well as power imbalances in personal relationships (Aksu, 2014: 40). While the traditional social structure unnecessarily glorifies masculinity, it can cause women to be treated as second-class "being women". Gender discrimination becomes especially evident in recruitment processes and may lead to candidates not being accepted to some positions simply because of their gender (Yüksel, 2005: 301-304).

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Women's involvement in working life is often met with the wrong perception that they will marry and have children, and that they will put their jobs on the back burner and therefore their jobs will not be given enough importance. The fact that women have more responsibilities at home than men has made it difficult for them to enter business life and often led them to work part-time jobs. Since they benefited less from education and job opportunities than men, they had to make do with low wages. Gender discrimination is also frequently encountered in career choices; Women generally turn to professions such as nursing and teaching due to environmental influences and pressures (Wirth, 2001: 13). The fact that women, who make up half of the world's population, have only 10% of the world's income shows how widespread gender discrimination is (Yiğit, 2018: 14). Situations such as keeping women's education level low, making it difficult or preventing them from accessing certain professions, and giving priority to single female employees in recruitment show the existence of gender discrimination in workplaces. Women are also at a more disadvantageous position compared to men in layoffs. The fact that unqualified workers who can be easily replaced are generally preferred during layoffs can be associated with the idea that women are not effective in providing for the family. As a result, patriarchal relationships and approaches in business life as well as at home cause women to be excluded from business life.

2. Sexual Harassment

Sexual harassment is generally defined as individuals with economic power or an important position sexually disturbing or putting the opposite sex in a difficult situation with immoral attitudes and behaviors (Sarmaşık, 2009: 4-5). Any sexually derogatory words or actions repeated in the workplace and made without the consent of the person may cause the employee to be in a difficult situation. Sexual harassment, in its broadest sense, is defined as any disturbing behavior against the sexuality, decency and chastity of an individual or individuals, verbally, visually or through body movements, without their consent (Sarmaşık, 2009: 7-8). Sexual harassment has been defined in various ways in scientific publications. One of the common points is that the person is subjected to sexual behavior even though he does not allow such behavior with his free will (Blumenthal, 1998: 33-57). All kinds of unwanted verbal or physical sexual advances, humiliating or sexually discriminatory expressions that may cause the person exposed to harassment to be afraid, intimidated or humiliated and negatively affect the working environment can also be defined as (Yiğit, 2018: 15).

3. Mobbing

The English term "mobbing" originates from "mob". The word "mob" refers to a group, mass or gang that unlawfully commits violence. Mobbing means psychological violence, siege, mass attack, discomfort and distress (Duffy and Sperry, 2011). Mobbing means psychological violence and emotional harassment. When implemented in the workplace, mobbing not only negatively affects performance, but also negatively affects the psychological health of the employee. The mental health of people exposed to mobbing is also affected. Mobbing, which occurs in organizations, in upper-

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subordinate vertical relationships or horizontal relationships, can apply to both men and women. However, it has been observed that it is generally applied more on women. Research shows that 77% of mobbing victims are women (Ceylan, 2013: 41).

According to a study, mobbing at work; It manifests itself in the form of changing tasks negatively, assigning tasks that will negatively affect performance, social exclusion methods such as exclusion and not communicating, humiliation and ridicule, public humiliation or negative criticism (Hartig and Frosch, 2006: 2).

People who may pose a danger within the organization are generally talented, well-equipped, committed, intelligent, honest, hard-working and successful individuals. Such people are more likely to be exposed to mobbing. Individuals with developed emotional intelligence who have the ability to make mistakes and correct these mistakes can become the target of mobbing behavior in a competitive environment. According to another view, people who cannot show adequate performance and experience constant failure are more likely to be exposed to mobbing in a competitive environment (Ünal, 2018: 13-14). The extreme stress experienced by an employee exposed to mobbing creates significant costs for the employer. However, employers' denial of mobbing may prevent them from raising awareness of such behavior. Mobbing is like a disease that spreads in workplaces; If precautions are not taken, it may affect all activities of the organization. The employee's confidence in the workplace and his colleagues decreases, motivation decreases, disharmony begins in the work environment, and productivity decreases. When women enter the workplace, they may be perceived by some men as interfering with their work. As a common thought among men, the fact that a woman needs a job while a man can support his own family may be considered by some men as a situation that may cause mobbing (Öztürk, 2007: 57).

In business life, if a woman is in a higher position than her male colleague, men can sometimes apply psychological mobbing to replace her. This may take the form of forcing oneself to hold oneself responsible outside of work, with sentences such as "You go do the housework, take care of your child, make dinner." Mobbing is a method that can be applied in every sector and at any time, and is especially used to alienate women from work. When women want to take part in business life, they have to face these difficulties. Even when they are exposed to mobbing by their managers, they should stand tall, not give up and not give up (Bulut and Göktürk, 2012: 54-63).

4. Glass Ceiling

The term "glass ceiling" is a concept that emerged in the USA in the 1970s and describes invisible and artificial barriers created by organizational prejudices that prevent women from rising to senior management positions (Wirth, 2001: 1). The document in which the term was first used was a news article on "Women in Business Life" published in the Wall Street Journal by Hymovtz and Schellard in 1986. In this news, the term glass ceiling refers to the difficulties faced by women who strive to reach senior management positions in a wide range of sectors, from businesses to government, from educational institutions to non-profit organizations (Sönmez and Bayraktar, 2017:

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6). A good example that can be used to explain the glass ceiling syndrome is the "flea experiment". Scientists have observed that fleas jump high. They took a few fleas and put them in a 30 cm high glass bowl. The metal floor under the bowl was heated and the fleas were disturbed.

Fleas jump trying to escape, but each time they hit their heads on the glass bowl and fall. Eventually, fleas learn to jump only about 30 cm. Over time, even if the obstacle of the glass bowl is removed, the fleas hesitate to jump high and do not dare, because they think that there is an obstacle in their minds. This situation is called "glass ceiling syndrome" (Sekman, 2005: 5). The reasons why female employees cannot advance in their organizations are generally non-objective criteria, and this causes the glass ceiling syndrome to have a negative impact on working life. Women face such barriers because of their gender and are prevented from advancing to senior management positions. Therefore, it is extremely important that organizational policies and practices are fair (Sönmez and Bayraktar, 2017: 22).

Glass ceilings are invisible obstacles faced by women who want to rise in the workplace and strive to achieve this goal. These obstacles include misperceptions such as women not caring about work or quitting their jobs when they get married. The term glass ceiling refers to the obstacles faced by women who want to rise to senior positions in various fields, from government institutions to companies, from educational institutions to non-profit organizations. Glass ceiling obstacles appear in various forms. These include wage inequality, job inequality, and gender discrimination at management levels. Wage inequality can be seen when even employees in similar positions receive different benefits and bonuses. Job inequality may arise from individuals' gender or ethnicity differences (Güner, 2011: 69). Gender discrimination in management levels refers to situations where it is difficult or impossible to move from middle to upper levels. With the increased participation of women in the workforce, research on women in business life and management has also increased. Previous research shows that female managers, especially in the private sector, often remain in middle-level positions. The reasons for the emergence of the glass ceiling include factors such as women's short stay in managerial positions, their low participation in the workforce, and the specific areas in which women traditionally work.

The glass ceiling refers to the obstacles women face as they begin to move up in their careers. This situation that occurs within the organization may create negativities in the feelings and behaviors of female employees. In the case of the glass ceiling, obstacles to women are examined in three main groups: obstacles put by male managers, obstacles put by female managers, and obstacles put by the individual himself (Ceylan, 2013: 36-37). The most important obstacle imposed by male managers is the prejudice against female employees. Some male managers may think that women have insufficient knowledge, determination or ideas about business. Another important obstacle is the idea of men having power; In other words, male managers generally prefer to be stronger than women and to be superior to them. In some cases, men may blame female employees' failures on themselves and even terminate their employment. Among the obstacles put up by female managers, perceptions about employees have an important place. For example, some female managers may think that because they are

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at senior levels, other women can be successful by following the same path. However, in some cases, there may be competition among female managers and some may try different tactics to surpass others. Finally, self-imposed barriers are also important. In this situation, women may limit their own careers based on their own abilities or lack of confidence in themselves. The existence of these barriers can make it difficult for women to advance in their careers and impact efforts to achieve gender equality in the workplace.

Obstacles that women put on themselves include thoughts such as accepting negative comments, feeling of guilt, lack of self-confidence, indecisiveness, not improving themselves, thinking that the system cannot change, and not wanting to advance in their career (Ceylan, 2013: 37). Due to these obstacles, some women may not want to take part in working life or may quit their jobs. However, this kind of thinking is not correct. The right thing to do is not to give up and not give up against the obstacles that come their way. It is about balancing family life and work life and keeping them organized. Institutions that want to make progress in this regard are taking various measures (Önder, 2013: 53). These may include:

- To encourage women to show tougher and more masculine attitudes.
- Demonstrating flexible approaches to women's special needs.
- Abandoning traditional methods and trying different approaches.
- Organizing campaigns against gender discrimination.

The aim of these methods is to increase women's job performance, advance their careers and help them overcome glass ceiling obstacles. Although some workplaces are taking steps in this regard, new legal regulations and positive discrimination practices regarding female management are required for a real solution to this problem.

5. Masculine Organizational Culture

The concept of organizational culture is a topic that was brought to the agenda with an article written by Andrew Pettgrew in 1979. Organizational culture is defined as the meaning system shared by a group and it is stated that it consists of myths, rituals, beliefs, ideology, language and symbols. Organizational culture functions as a system of common values that guide the behavior of employees. Organizational culture can also be called a system of shared values. It is an important value that gives identity to organizations and is effective in the success of the organization (Selmoğlu, 2019: 5-6). Organizational culture helps the organization realize its strategies and increase its efficiency. It ensures the consistency of employees' behavior within the organization. While organizational culture has such an important place in the institution you work in, it is seen that the organizational culture based on male dominance has negative effects on the business lives of working women. One of the problems of women in business life is the male-oriented organizational culture.

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The patriarchal structures of organizations in Turkey and the lack of social environments where socially responsible women can come together outside the corporate structure prevent women from meeting at a common point and growing their businesses (Yığıt, 2018: 18). Since women live in a male-dominated society, this situation also affects working life. Therefore, there are managers in workplaces who exclude women and make their lives difficult. Employers do not think that women can handle their job responsibilities because they see them only as a woman, wife, mother or someone who takes care of the housework. Another problem is that the priority given to men in education and women are generally pushed to the background in education, which emerges as a social obstacle. Just as importance is given to the education of men, the same importance should be given to the education of women and the education process should start in the family. The bureaucratic and hierarchical organizational structure prevents women from being effective in business life because under such structures, female employees cannot find enough space for themselves, or even if they do, they cannot show themselves. Since male employees prioritize their own desires for promotion, they do not give opportunities to female employees and do not want them to have a say. Women working in businesses with a male-dominated culture have difficulties over time and may even encounter negative situations such as mobbing.

6. Wage Inequality for Women

The labor of female employees is seen as worthless compared to the labor of male employees (Öztürk, 2007: 50). For this reason, even though men and women do the same job, there is a wage difference between them. Women often receive lower wages than their male counterparts and they have to accept this situation. Although the principle of equal pay for equal work has been legally adopted, organizations generally do not implement this rule. In times of economic crisis, the first target of layoffs is usually female employees. In addition, not paying equal wages for equal work not only causes gender-based low wage practices but also restricts working life. Since women are not given adequate education and support, they are directed to low value-added professions and even forced to do so due to lack of education. For this reason, women have to accept the low wages they receive. According to a study, the reason for this wage difference is that although male and female employees are the same age, women's working and career periods are shorter (Wirth, 2001: 29-32). This situation is thought to be related to the periods when women leave their jobs or work part-time due to reasons such as pregnancy and child care. When they return to work, it is observed that they are promoted more slowly and earn less. In addition, the lack of policies and practices to support mothers in general in workplaces is also noteworthy (Ceylan, 2013: 38). Thus, women feel that they are not valued enough, become unhappy, and consider quitting their jobs or even returning to working life again.

7. Assigning Simple Tasks

While women generally work in traditionally female professions throughout their careers, they avoid choosing jobs preferred by men. This situation prevents women

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from rising to senior management positions, making career plans and demanding higher wages. The traditional social structure makes it difficult for women to be less involved in business life due to reasons such as child care and housework that male-oriented gender roles place on women's shoulders. Due to this situation, women cannot fully benefit from the rights granted to them such as education, social security and promotion in the workplace. Instead, they are forced to settle for low-paying, part-time jobs. Low-status jobs, jobs with limited career development opportunities, jobs with low added value and satisfaction levels have restrictive and disturbing effects on female employees. These effects include mental and emotional stress, loss of motivation to work, reluctance to work, and a feeling of burnout. The first employees preferred for important jobs that require responsibility and are defined as difficult are always men (Ceylan, 2013: 39). Women, on the other hand, are excluded by being assigned to such jobs below their capacity. Especially when it comes to layoffs, the first preferred employees are usually women.

Gender-based determination of jobs and professions in the labor market generally directs women to traditionally female professions. Although there are open positions, they cannot apply for jobs that are generally considered men's jobs. This situation causes women to accept lower status and lower paid jobs. In this way, women's labor is relegated to a secondary position and seen as worthless. Low status jobs generally appear as low wages, temporary jobs and jobs without social security (Ceylan, 2013: 38).

8. Risks in the Working Environment

Tools used in jobs that require physical strength can cause muscle strain and various health problems. The materials used may pose a risk to life and property safety. In jobs where women work intensively, health problems such as wear and tear in areas such as neck, shoulders, arms, waist, back, legs and wrists are frequently observed. For example, jobs such as lifting heavy loads in a factory environment can be given as an example. "Tenosynovitis (tendon sheath inflammation) is frequently seen among women working in the food industry, and carpal tunnel syndrome is frequently seen among garment workers, hotel workers and those working in the service sector" (Esin and Öztürk, 2015: 4). The architectural features of the working environment and the tools used should be arranged ergonomically not only for male employees but also for female employees. Comfortable working environments should be provided for both women and men, ergonomic furniture should be preferred and a healthy, peaceful working environment should be created.

9. Emotional Consequences

Emotion is the echo, effect, reaction and impression that an event, person or object evokes in a person's inner world. Emotions, which are one of the basic determinants of human behavior, are divided into two categories: internal emotions that are innate and biological in origin, and internal emotions acquired through life experience. Inner emotions are emotions that are innate and an integral part of human nature. Emotions

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such as anger, sadness, fear, pleasure, love, surprise, learning and shame are universally accepted (Hacızade, 2012: 7-8). Non-intrinsic emotions, on the other hand, are emotions that are acquired with age and gained through experience. Emotions such as honor, compassion, embarrassment, empathy, virtue, and appreciation are examples of this category. People use their emotional mechanisms to respond appropriately or adapt to various events they encounter throughout their lives. In this context, it is important to give the most appropriate emotional response to the events that people encounter in their lives. It is necessary to learn which emotion to use in which situation and to be sensitive about it. Emotion management is defined as controlling people's emotional fluctuations, preventing random emotionality, ensuring that the mind prevails over emotions, and directing the mind and emotions correctly (Töremen and Çankaya, 2008: 34).

We must start emotional management by knowing ourselves. Then we must evaluate our current situation and conditions. Because a significant part of the emotional problems people experience arise from reacting to events with wrong emotions. It is important to maintain a calm attitude. In this way, the feeling of burnout experienced by people can be prevented or the number of people experiencing burnout can be reduced. Problems in private or business life can lead people to sadness and pessimism. This can also cause people to become more angry and intolerant. Two important behavioral patterns in terms of emotionality at the interpersonal level attract attention: while angry and aggressive behaviors damage relationships, people's withdrawn, distant, insensitive and mechanical attitudes can alienate them from their environment. This situation may cause people to feel burnout over time. On a personal level, anxiety, sadness, pessimism, and mood swings can be common. The person may feel anxious and tense, have poor emotional control, and cry for no reason. In interpersonal relationships, individuals may prefer a closed, stagnant, distant and unemotional communication when listening to and understanding the other person. This situation can prevent the development of healthy relationships and create disconnection between people.

This shows how important emotional management is in working life. People who cannot manage their emotions effectively in the work and study environment begin to doubt their profession and feel powerless. They begin to feel that they lack support in managing their emotions and begin to lose their self-esteem. This may cause them to display an angry and hurtful attitude towards their colleagues and superiors. As a result, the person begins to constantly blame the people around him at work and in the work environment, and this may reflect a state of complete emotional exhaustion. The emotional symptoms of emotional burnout can be diverse and lead to mental health problems such as anxiety and depression. These symptoms may include feelings such as resentment, obvious sadness, an apathetic appearance, unfounded suspicions and paranoia, decrease in self-esteem and self-confidence, feeling of failure, guilt and helplessness (Ceylan, 2013: 13). Other symptoms of emotional burnout in people who experience a sense of failure include emotional exhaustion, constant worry and panic, chronic irritability, irritability, cognitive difficulties, frustration, demoralization, anxiety, restlessness, impatience, low self-esteem, feeling of worthlessness, intolerance

of criticism, decision-making. It may occur as difficulty giving in, apathy, feeling of emptiness and hopelessness (Eroğlu, 2014: 153). Previous studies have revealed that service sector employees who experience high levels of emotional burnout are more prone to depression than employees who experience moderate and low levels of burnout or no burnout (Çoban, 2014: 68).

One of the important consequences of burnout is a decrease in an individual's energy level, which can lead to resorting to harmful habits such as painkillers, sleeping pills, tranquilizers or alcohol to cope with the challenges of daily life. This situation affects the individual's mental health and may also lead to a decrease in the individual's sense of success and self-esteem (Yiğit, 2018: 56).

10. Physical Results

Physical consequences manifest themselves in various symptoms (Ceylan, 2013: 11-12). These; physical symptoms, psychosomatic symptoms, physiological symptoms. Physical Symptoms: It manifests itself as physical symptoms in men such as headache, muscle and joint pain, tension in the nerves, constant feeling of tiredness, weakness, constantly being sick and feeling sick, dry throat, shortness of breath, sudden weight changes, sleep problems and sexual problems. Physical health problems include diseases such as chronic fatigue, insomnia, headaches, digestive problems, various illnesses, coronary heart disease, respiratory disorders and persistent colds (Çoban, 2014: 68). All these physical symptoms have a negative impact on people's lives. While individuals exposed to these situations did not experience such symptoms in their lives before, the fact that they begin to experience such symptoms over time may mean that they are experiencing burnout syndrome.

Individuals feel tired and weak, especially at work and during work, and become unable to do work and experience reluctance. People find themselves in a state of fatigue that does not go away over time and begin not to enjoy life. This is a sign that they are starting to experience burnout.

Psychosomatic Symptoms: It is known that the conflicts and disappointments people experience lead to physical disorders. Psychological factors underlie these diseases, which are called "psychosomatic" in the medical literature. It seems that people's low morale plays an important role in the increase of these disorders. Psychosomatic symptoms that occur in the human body include: Heart palpitations, dry throat and mouth, dizziness, extreme fatigue, tremors, nervous tics, startle, stuttering, impaired expression, teeth grinding, nail biting, sleep disorder, sweating, frequent urination. Symptoms such as heartburn, nausea, constipation, headaches and backaches, neck stiffness, loss of appetite or excessive appetite may be observed.

Psychosomatic diseases include conditions such as stomach pains, heart diseases, diabetes, high-low blood pressure, hair loss, skin diseases, and migraines that cannot be attributed to a specific reason (Eroğlu, 2015: 94-95). Diseases such as asthma, colitis, allergic reactions, cold and flu can also be considered in the psychosomatic category.

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Headaches and high blood pressure are among the important psychosomatic consequences of burnout. Diabetes is also a psychosomatic consequence of burnout. Burnout is seen as an important factor in the development of excess cholesterol (hypercholesterolemia) and diabetes. Musculoskeletal disorders are also among the psychosomatic consequences of burnout. It is observed that musculoskeletal pain is more common in individuals with high levels of burnout (Yılmaz and Biçkes, 2014: 43). The stress and troubles that individuals experience in their work and private lives can lead to burnout by disrupting their body balance and reducing their quality of life over time. These conditions can cause health problems such as cancer, heart diseases, high blood pressure and diabetes. Because the stress and troubles experienced by individuals can turn into physical diseases.

Physiological Symptoms: The main goal of all living things is to survive. In the second half of the 19th century, French physiologist Claude Bernard stated that all living things try to keep their internal environment constant despite changes in the external environment.

As a result of his research on humans and laboratory animals, Walter B. Cannon found that tension, which he called "stress" in the fight and flight responses, leads to various physiological reactions. Emotions such as fear, anger, enthusiasm and excitement require internal physiological reactions. These reactions include physiological changes such as increased heart rate and increased levels of fat and sugar in the blood.

When the body is under excessive stress, the individual's adaptation energy decreases and he feels extremely tired. Over time, this energy runs out and the individual may lose his will and desire. Stress, a physiological concept, is based on the studies of scientists such as Bernard, Cannon and Selye (Eroğlu, 2015: 503-506). Selye stated that the body's stress response occurs in a certain process, and he called the mechanism that covers the physiological changes that occur in this process "general adaptation syndrome". This syndrome consists of three stages: The first stage is the alarm response, that is, the stage in which physiological reactions occur. The body may show slight tension during this phase. The second phase is the resistance phase and chemical changes occur in the body. If severe stress continues, the third phase, exhaustion, occurs. In this phase, the person moves towards a state of exhaustion and his adaptation energy is exhausted (Eroğlu, 2015: 505-506).

Within the framework of today's neo-liberal policies, due to working conditions that increasingly work against workers, many employees experience burnout syndrome, especially because they cannot cope with the stress factors produced by business life. This situation causes extreme fatigue. Over time, the cells of individuals whose energy is depleted begin to show signs of aging and burnout becomes inevitable. **Mental Consequences:** Mental problems experienced by individuals cause them to experience burnout over time. Mental problems can negatively affect individuals' lives and cause them to make mistakes. This can cause them to lose their ability to solve problems. As a result, individuals may experience burnout and give up on everything if they cannot cope with these problems. Individuals experiencing burnout syndrome may experience

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mental distraction, forgetfulness, lack of planning, tendency to constantly make mistakes, dependent and limited thought capacity, stereotyped thinking style, decrease and disconnections in interpersonal communication and decision-making skills (Yiğit, 2018: 53). Additionally, there may be difficulties in coping with situations that arise from being alone. Perceptual disorders may also occur over time and a feeling of learned helplessness may develop. Perceptual disorders can be defined as the partial or complete loss of a person's motor skills and, accordingly, the loss of abilities such as comprehension, reasoning and analysis. Psychological and cognitive processes often underlie such disorders.

When a person experiences psychological negativities, perception disorders may occur. One of the important mental consequences observed in individuals exposed to burnout syndrome is the phenomenon of "learned helplessness". Learned helplessness is when an individual constantly experiences failure in a situation, thinks that nothing will change no matter what he does, that events are not under his control and that he will not be successful in the future, and therefore avoids new attempts. An individual's past negative experiences can affect their future attitudes and behavior. Those who experience learned helplessness may first lose their passion for life. Later, thinking and reasoning abilities may weaken. In the final stage, a weakening of emotional reactions can also be observed (Sekman, 2005: 30-31). A well-known example of learned helplessness is as follows: A few small fish and one large fish are placed in an aquarium. Big fish eat small fish when they get hungry. Then a glass is placed in the middle of the aquarium, in this case the big fish cannot reach the small fish even if they want to. The glass is removed after 48 hours, but the big fish no longer tries to eat the small fish; it does not go where there is no glass, it acts as if it still exists. Scientists have called this situation "learned helplessness" (Sekman, 2005: 8-13-14). Individuals experiencing burnout syndrome may encounter various obstacles in expressing their thoughts and beliefs in meeting their basic needs such as shelter, nutrition, health and education. Efforts to overcome these obstacles may be insufficient and the person may give up on everything over time. In this process, the person may develop learned helplessness.

H. Policy Implementations for Working Mothers in Different Welfare State Models

The welfare system is an inevitable structure consisting of state, market and family components, and is important for both society and citizenship. Much of people's well-being is determined by the family and the market. Income is usually obtained from the market, and social support is mostly obtained from the family. However, as women's participation in the workforce increases, there is a natural increase in the demand for child and elderly care. The domestic care option is losing its effectiveness as in the past, because a decrease in the number of potential people who can provide care labor is observed. In this case, with the disappearance of traditional care structures, the welfare state comes to the fore as the only alternative (Esping-Andersen, 2011: 105-106). In this context, policies aimed at solving the problems that arise as different welfare states move away from their traditional roles should be examined. Issues such as how welfare states can meet the new social needs arising from the increased participation of women

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in the workforce, how they can provide access to care services, and how their role in the family can be redefined should be emphasized. These policies should be considered from a broad perspective such as gender equality, labor market balance and sustainability of social security systems.

The family-related policies of welfare states first appear in their reflections in international documents that require women to have equal status with men. The important provisions of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 10 December 1948, in terms of equality between men and women are as follows: "Declaring that all human beings are born free and equal (Article 1); that they may enjoy all the rights and freedoms declared in the Declaration, without distinction of language, religion, political or any other belief, national or social origin, wealth, birth or any other distinction, and that there will be no discrimination for this reason; that all are equal before the law and are entitled without discrimination to the equal protection of the law, that everyone is entitled to equal protection against any discrimination contrary to this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination (Article 7); These are the provisions regulating that "every person shall have the right to freely choose his/her job, to fair and favorable working conditions and protection from unemployment, and to equal pay for equal work without any discrimination (Article 23)" (Ertürk, 2008: 66). There are 9 basic human rights conventions at the United Nations level. The contract that focuses on gender equality is the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. Article 4 of this contract states "1. Temporary and special measures to be taken by the State Parties to ensure de facto equality of men and women will not be considered as discrimination of the kind specified in this Convention and will not in any way result in inequality or the maintenance of different standards. These measures will be discontinued when the objectives of equality of opportunity and practice are achieved. 2. Special measures to be taken by States Parties for the protection of maternity, including those specified in this Convention, shall not be considered discriminatory." (Ayata, Dilek and Oder, 2010: 139).

Adopting the principle that everyone is equal before the law and has the right to equal protection, the member states of the Council of Europe adopted the principle of non-discrimination in order to take new measures to ensure that everyone has equal rights in the prohibition of discrimination through the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, signed on 4 November 1950. confirmed that it does not prevent measures to be taken to ensure effective and full equality if there are justified and reasonable grounds (Ayata et al., 2010: 172). It is known that all member states of the European Union are members of the International Labor Organization (ILO). In this context, there are articles on gender equality in the International Labor Organization documents. In this regard, ILO Convention No. 100 states: "Each Member State shall, by means in accordance with the procedures in force for the determination of wage levels, promote the principle of equality of remuneration between male and female workers for work of equal value and shall ensure that this principle applies to all workers; this shall be ensured by national legislation, Any wage determination system established or recognized by legislation may be implemented through collective

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agreements between employers and workers or by combining these various procedures (Article 2.)" (Kaya, 2012: 39).

In ILO Convention No. 156 on the Equal Treatment and Provision of Equal Opportunities for Male and Female Workers with Family Responsibilities, it is emphasized that the problems of workers with family responsibilities are part of the issues related to society and family life and the necessity of regulating this issue in international policies. The contract also states that male and female employees with family responsibilities should be provided with equal opportunities and treated equally (Kaya, 2012: 45). In the ILO Convention No. 11 dated 1958 on Discrimination in Regards to Labor and Profession, it is regulated that member states should determine and implement national policies to end all kinds of discrimination in profession and working life and ensure equality of opportunity in accordance with national practices (Kaya, 2012: 40). Along with the emphasis on equality between men and women, the concept of family is also legally regulated in many welfare states and international documents. Modern welfare states are primarily based on the family. Post-war social policies adopted the family model in which the woman did the housework and the man provided the family.

This explains why welfare states have historically been inadequate in providing income support and social services. Scandinavian countries have adopted a new approach by giving priority to family services since the 1970s. In the UK and North America, governments have encouraged market alternatives partly through tax cuts. In Europe, the principle of familism has been accepted by excluding child care services, especially in countries such as France and Belgium (Esping-Andersen, 2011: 107). When compared to Europe in terms of women's participation in business life and family-related policies, it is known that Turkey has more supportive policies.

There are various regulations regarding pregnancy and maternity leaves at national and international levels. The International Labor Organization's (ILO) Revised Convention No. 103 on Maternity Protection and Maternity Protection Convention No. 183 regulate pregnancy and maternity leaves. While the duration of a woman's maternity leave was determined as at least twelve weeks in Convention No. 103, this period was increased to fourteen weeks with Convention No. 183 (Kaya, 2012: 43).

European Union Directives include the Directive No. 92/85/EEC on the Development of Measures to Promote the Improvement of Occupational Health and Safety of Pregnant, Postpartum or Lactating Employees and the regulations regarding the pregnancy and postpartum status of female employees. According to this directive, member states must ensure that pregnant, maternity or lactating employees benefit from a maximum of fourteen weeks of leave before and after birth. Maternity leave must be mandatory for at least two weeks, with some of it taken before and/or after the birth. In addition, pregnant employees should be given permission in accordance with the legislation so that they can perform the necessary examinations during working hours (Ertürk, 2008: 115). Directive 96/34EC and Directive 97/75/EC on the Framework

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Convention on Parental Leave, concluded by UNICE, CEEP and ETUC, regulate parental leave and unified policies have been developed in this context.

According to the Convention, male and female employees are granted at least three months of parental leave for an age period up to the age of eight to be determined by the member states or social partners, in order to care for their children due to birth or adoption (Art.2/1). In addition, member states and/or social partners are obliged to take the necessary measures in accordance with the collective agreement and national legislation in case the employee cannot come to work due to urgent family obligations (Article 3/1) (Ertürk, 2008: 118). Compared to European countries, maternity leave durations vary considerably. Germany and Sweden stand out with paid maternity leave periods of up to 47 weeks. Norway allows 44 weeks of unpaid leave to working mothers, Greece for 34 weeks, Finland for 32 weeks, and Canada for 29 weeks. In the USA, there is a 14-week maternity leave practice, and this country ranks last in this regard. As stated before, Turkey provides working mothers with the right to 16 weeks of unpaid leave (Tuuç, 2015: 125).

In France, child care covers 40% of children under three years of age, but only half of these children are enrolled in centres; the remainder are cared for by individual caregivers. In Scandinavian countries, high-quality, full-day care is provided to all children. This practice requires significant government assistance, with parents covering 33% of the cost and low-income parents paying no fee (Esping-Andersen, 2011: 181). The existence of paid parental leave in Northern European countries and the promotion of "father months" that only fathers can use greatly increase the rate of fathers' use of leave (Nyberg, 2010; cited in İlkkaracan, 2018: 48). In the Netherlands, the option of using parental leave as part-time work is seen as an encouraging practice for men. Some men may have difficulty in not completely leaving the workforce and taking on full-time care duties at home due to the influence of gender roles (Plantenga, 2010; cited in İlkkaracan, 2018: 48). The policy in Denmark is one of the policies that provides the best home-work harmony. These policies make it possible for all mothers with young children to continue working. Typically, a Danish mother can use the first year after the birth of the child as a leave and then return to full-time work after working part-time for a short period (Esping-Andersen, 2011: 126).

I. Regulations Made for Mothers in Business Life in Turkey

Turkish women first took their place in working life with the midwifery training they received in 1843. Women, who started working actively as paid workers in 1897, gained the right to become civil servants in 1913. In this process, they also found a place for themselves in the economy as tradesmen and merchants. The reforms carried out with the proclamation of the Republic significantly changed the position of women in society. Many laws regarding women have been brought to the agenda and reviewed during the process. In order to carry out women-related policies more systematically, the Advisory Board on Policies for Women was established in 1987, and then the General Directorate on the Status of Women was established in 1990 and restructured

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in 2004 (Gül et al., 2014: 170). The Ministry of Family and Social Policies, which was established in 2011, continued its work in the field of women by taking the name of the Ministry of Family, Labor and Social Services in 2018.

The articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Turkey, which is at the top of the hierarchy of norms, are arranged in line with the principle of equality between men and women. Article 10 of the Constitution states that "Everyone is equal before the law, without discrimination based on language, race, colour, gender, political thought, philosophical belief, religion, sect or similar reasons." This provision has a character that strengthens this principle. With the constitutional amendment made in 2010, the same article was added: "Women and men have equal rights. The state is obliged to ensure that this equality is realized. Measures to be taken for this purpose cannot be interpreted as contrary to the principle of equality." The statement aims to guarantee the position of women in society by the state. Additionally, in order to prevent women from being in a secondary position within the family, Article 41 of the Constitution states that "Family is the foundation of Turkish society and is based on equality between spouses." There is a provision (Metin and Kariman, 2013). Article 5 of the Labor Law No. 4857 is regulated under the title "Principle of Equal Treatment". According to this article, no discrimination can be made in business relationships based on reasons such as language, race, gender, political opinion, philosophical belief, religion and sect. The employer cannot take different actions, directly or indirectly, due to gender or pregnancy, unless biological or nature-related reasons make it necessary. In addition, setting lower wages for jobs of the same or equal value due to gender or applying special protective provisions due to the gender of the worker is also prohibited (Labor Law No. 4857, Article 5). These regulations constitute the basic legal framework to ensure equality between men and women and prevent discrimination in Turkey.

However, these periods are among the protective provisions for female workers. Additionally, there are certain obligations that employers must comply with for female workers. For example, Article 24 of the Labor Law No. 4857, Article II. Clause d states that the employer is obliged to take the necessary measures in case the employee is sexually harassed at the workplace, and that the employee has the right to leave the job for a justified reason if he reports this situation. Similarly, Article 25 of the same law, Article II. Clause c regulates that the employer has the right to dismiss for justified reason if the employee sexually harasses another employee. In case of maternity, Article 74 of the Labor Law No. 4857 is regulated under the title "Work and Nursing Leave in Case of Maternity". Accordingly, female workers are provided with a total of sixteen weeks of leave, eight weeks before birth and eight weeks after birth. In case of multiple pregnancy, two weeks are added to the eight weeks before birth. This regulation gives female workers time to provide the necessary health and care during birth and postpartum periods and enables them to take a break from working life. As a result, the protective provisions of the Labor Law No. 4857 for female workers constitute an important legal framework for the prevention of gender-based discrimination and the equal participation of women in working life. However, in some cases, it is criticized that these provisions should be implemented in more detail and effectively.

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These provisions regulate the rights provided to female workers in Turkey during the pre- and post-natal periods. According to the relevant articles of the Labor Law No. 4857, female workers have the opportunity to work in the workplace up to three weeks before giving birth, but this period is determined by a doctor's report and is required to be suitable for their health condition. The days worked during this period are added to the postpartum leave period. During the pre- and post-natal periods, these periods may be increased depending on the health of the worker and the nature of the job. The worker is given paid leave for periodic check-ups during pregnancy and can be employed in light work if his/her health condition is suitable; In this case, there is no reduction in the worker's wage. Additionally, postpartum female workers are given optional unpaid leave of up to six months after completion of sixteen weeks of leave. This period shall not be taken into account in calculating the entitlement to paid annual leave. These regulations were made to enable female workers in Turkey to balance their work life during the pre- and post-natal periods, to enable them to meet their health needs and to support them in harmonizing family life and work life. However, it is important that these rights are implemented effectively and that workers are aware of these rights.

The right to breastfeeding leave regulated in the Labor Law No. 4857 provides that female workers are given a total of one and a half hours of breastfeeding leave per day to breastfeed their children under the age of one. This time can be determined by the worker himself, and it can be decided between which hours and how many times it will be divided. Additionally, this time is counted as daily working time. Article 88 of Law No. 4857 states that the employment conditions of pregnant or breastfeeding women and the regulations regarding breastfeeding rooms and child care dormitories will be determined by the regulation to be prepared by the Ministry of Labor and Social Security. This regulation is created with the opinion of the Ministry of Health and regulates issues such as which jobs pregnant or breastfeeding women can be employed in and how breastfeeding rooms or nurseries should be established. On the other hand, Article 14 of Law No. 1475 includes situations that entitle people to severance pay, and it also regulates the situation in which a woman quits her job due to marriage. This provision continues to be valid despite the entry into force of Law No. 4857. These regulations support the protection of women's rights in business life in Turkey in the pre- and post-natal periods, the provision of working conditions appropriate to their health status, and their ability to balance their family responsibilities and business life. The regulation stated in the legal regulations regarding women leaving their jobs voluntarily is subject to some criticism. This regulation is considered as a factor that may pave the way for women to withdraw from the labor market or quit their jobs. Regarding women's leaving the job after marriage, social norms and family pressures are effective and can be interpreted as an incentive for women to be removed from business life. This may reflect a mentality in which women are encouraged to stay at home and fulfill their motherhood role, and this role is highlighted.

Statistics on the effectiveness of welfare policies in Turkey show that the proportion of families where both parents work is low. For example, the proportion of children in families where only one parent works is quite high. In this case, it is generally seen that

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the working parents are fathers. These statistics reveal that women's participation in the workforce is limited in Turkey and that they are generally held responsible for care services due to their gender roles. In this context, the necessity of more comprehensive policies and practices to strengthen the place of women in the labor market and ensure gender equality in Turkey is emphasized. Such policies will be important steps to encourage women to take an active role in working life, to combat gender discrimination in workplaces and to enable women to overcome the work-power divide.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to examine the effects of working mothers' perceptions of work-family balance on their psychological health and work performance. The findings obtained as a result of literature review and comprehensive data analysis provided important information.

The findings obtained in our study show that there is an important relationship between work-family balance and psychological health. Improving work-family balance may help reduce stress levels and reduce symptoms of depression in working mothers. Other studies in the literature also support these findings and reveal that maintaining work-family balance has positive effects on the general psychological health of individuals.

The impact of working mothers' work-family balance perceptions on their work performance also emerged as an important finding. Employees who can maintain a good work-family balance can demonstrate higher performance at work and manage their work more effectively. This is also an important indicator for employers because the motivation and commitment of employees who can maintain work-family balance increases. Based on the results of the study, it is emphasized that policies and practices that support work-family balance should be developed. Employers can help working mothers achieve work-family balance by offering supportive measures such as flexible working hours, remote working opportunities, and child care services. It is also recommended to organize programs to manage stress and reduce work-family conflict for working mothers.

Some limitations should also be taken into consideration within the scope of this study. For example, participants had limited demographic characteristics or working mothers' perceptions of work-family balance were based on subjective evaluations. Future studies should be conducted with larger and more diverse groups of participants and should be designed to assess long-term effects.

This study should be considered as a step towards understanding the complex effects of working mothers' perceptions of work-family balance on their psychological health and work performance. The findings emphasize the contributions of work-family balance to the overall quality of life and work life of employees.

RESTRICTION

Since national and international resources and scientific research are sufficient, no restrictions are stated on the subject.

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